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An expression screen to identify genes that modify disease severity in triple negative breast cancer.

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Race is explicitly described and implicitly understood to be a strong determinant of disease severity in human cancer including TNBC but haplotype-dependent/resultant contributions to the tumor transcriptome in humans remain poorly understood.

We measured total transcription in the primary tumor with RNA-sequencing in black or white humans with triple negative breast cancer (TNBC) to define in an unbiased manner and comprehensively the contributions of genetic background and race-related differences in haplotype structure to the primary tumor transcriptome in humans with cancer.

Results

Identify disease modifying genes in human cancer: genes likely to (or with expression difference suggesting ability of the identified gene to) significantly influence tumor biology, and modify disease severity and/or progression in TNBC

Identify genes that are important for the cell biologic and transcriptional functions of the tumor in humans with TNBC, irrespective of genetic background: genes likely to be important in the tumor life cycle or for cancer cell functions based on a. baseMean indicating production of a quantity of transcript that reflects an amount reflecting biological importance of the gene product (ie., not lacking in differential expression because the gene is generally not expressed in any significant quantity in the tumor) and b. transcriptome wide differential expression demonstrating a lack of change in transcript expression when comparing tumor transcriptomes based on genetic background in humans, indicating that the gene is expressed in the tumors of humans with TNBC but not that this tumor expression does not considerably vary based on the genetic background (genes that belong to race-associated haplotypes, here identified based on study of $n=16$ white females and $n=19$ black females) together suggesting that expression of the identified gene is likely relevant/important in tumor biology or the tumor life cycle.

Note 1: Transcriptional evidence indicating the speed of the cancer cell cycle in black females is generally and significantly higher than in white females, in human TNBC.

A composite network of genes representing a transcriptional pattern indicative of proliferative capacity (speed of cell cycle) was appreciated. These genes included the proliferation marker MKI67, thymidine kinase 1 (encoded by TK1), a nucleotide synthesis enzyme and recently defined primary expression component of the solid tumor in humans, genes functioning in cell division included the aurora kinases AURKA and AURKB as well as BUB1B, and the cyclin dependent kinases (CDKs) CDK6 and CDK2, each of which was expressed at higher quantity in the primary tumor in black women, and the increased expression of which were representative features describing influence of the haplotype (genetic background) on tumor transcriptome in TNBC. Nearly all histone subunits whose expression was measured were unilaterally and preferentially activated in the primary tumors of black women. Interestingly, a gene that functions at the level of cytokinesis during cell division, ANLN, a gene we and others defined as a signature differentially expressed gene of the TNBC solid tumor in humans, was present at significantly higher quantity in the tumors of black women, together suggesting that some composite feature that imparted an enhanced cycling phenotype that was itself associated with triple negative breast cancer in humans was enhanced by and more closely associated with the genetic background of black humans.

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Note 2: Differences in expression of genes functioning in amino acid metabolism, endosomal and lysosomal signaling associated with or functioning in feedback signaling resulting from nutrient sensing.

Tbc family activation influenced or controlled by genetic background, as well as multiple components of the mTOR amino acid sensing energy pathway were key differences that distinguished the TNBC tumor transcriptome.

1 This note also describes evidence demonstrating differences in associated activity resulting from
2 expression of genes belonging to SLC solute carrier channel genes, and genes functioning in
3 metabolically-oriented vesicular transport of the Rab, Sec and Vps families.

4 A transcript encoded by the gene SPAAR was a feature of nutrient sensing distinguished by
5 race-associated human haplotype in the primary tumors in humans with TNBC.

6 Note 3: Intrinsic differences in homeobox expression resulting from the human genetic background in
7 TNBC.

8 This included homeobox factors of the Tcf, Tbx, Fox, Lhx, and Hmg TF families, among others. These
9 findings expand considerably to our previous study of homeobox expression in TNBC describing Zfhx2 as
10 a homeobox factor expressed preferentially in the tumors of black women with TNBC. This, even within a
11 defined subtype, homeobox expression varies to an appreciable extent in human cancer and is controlled
12 by genetic factors belonging to race-associated haplotype structures.

13 Note 4: Immunologically relevant gene expression in the triple negative breast cancer tumor and
14 differences in expression of these genes resulting from genetic background (race).

15 This included among other genes surface markers CD320 and CD302, Ly family lymphocyte antigen
16 expression, a group of immune receptors consisting of multiple immunoglobulin-like receptors, including
17 SIGLEC genes SIGLEC1 and SIGLEC9 which were preferentially expressed in human TNBC in the
18 primary tumors of white women, but with preferential expression of IGSF3 and AMIGO1 in the TNBC
19 primary tumor in black women. Genes that function in antigen presentation including ERAP1, genes
20 functioning in interferon signaling including Isg20L2 and MX2, haplotype-dependent expression of
21 complement pathway molecules in the primary tumor including C7 and CFH, interleukin genes IL16 and
22 IL20RA, CXCL12, and as well as immunologically oriented tumor expression events we find to be general
23 characteristics of the TNBC tumor transcriptome in humans but not differing based on genetic background,
24 like that of CD5.

25 Note 5: Genes (endonucleases, exonucleases, and others) that participate in DNA repair and replication
26 processes and at the telomere are expressed differently in white and black humans with TNBC.

27 This included the Holliday junction enzyme HJURP, endonucleases SLX1A, SLX1B and SLX9, ERI3
28 exonuclease, FEN1, Rad pathway genes, H2AX, among many others.

A group of genes that each function in telomere repair, maintenance of telomere biology, and which differs
considerably in the TNBC tumor transcriptome in white and black humans, including Rif1 is described
here.

Note 6: Transcriptional differences in molecules that function in cell survival and cell death signaling in
human TNBC.

These differences in tumor expression of molecules that function in cell survival included necroptotic and
apoptotic kinase genes MLKL and RIPK3. BIRC2, an apoptotic regulator and the cell death-associated
molecule mitochondrial PGAM5 were also genes whose expression defined the TNBC tumor
transcriptome and resulted from factors in the genetic background in white and black humans. CFLAR, a
cell death regulator, was expressed at significant quantity in human TNBC but CFLAR expression was not
different in white and black women.

Note 7: Hormone receptor signaling is fundamentally different in humans with TNBC as a result of the
human genetic background.

We recently described biologically significant activation of hormone receptors ESR1 and PGR1 in
Rb1-deficient TNBC. We describe here differences in expression of the hormone receptors ESR1 and
PGR1 that were defining characteristics of the tumor transcriptome in TNBC: ESR1 and PGR1, though

1 present at relatively low levels, were significantly activated in the primary tumors of white women with
2 TNBC. Concomitant with haplotype-dependent activation of hormone receptor expression in white women,
3 we discovered steroid hormone pathway activation in the primary tumor as a central feature of
4 haplotype-dependent tumor transcriptome in black women with TNBC, including activation of the
5 expression of reductase genes of the DHCR family, hydroxysteroid (HSD) family genes, and cytochrome
6 genes of the CYB family.

7 Note 8: Human growth hormone is produced in significantly higher quantities in the tumor in black women
8 with TNBC.

9 Note 9: Epigenetic regulation in human cancer when studied according to race-associated haplotype.

10 This included polycomb complex genes EZH2 and PCGF6, JMJD4, bromodomain-associated molecules
11 BICRA, CBX5, MBD3, and others.

12 Note 10: Axon guidance activation in black women with TNBC.

13 We discovered a significant pattern of axon guidance molecule induction in black women with TNBC,
14 including prominent Ephrin pathway ligands and receptors.

15 Note 11: Nuclear transport is activated in human TNBC in a haplotype-specific manner.

16 The tumor transcriptomes of black women with TNBC featured high expression of nuclear import receptors
17 IPO4 and IPO13, RNA nuclear export receptor Aly/Ref, TNPO3, nuclear pore complex subunits Nup93
18 and Nup133, and other significant differences in nuclear transport pathway gene expression. Genetic
19 background associated with human race regulates aspects of cellular trafficking in the tumor in human
20 cancer.

21 Note 12: ERBB2 and ERBB3 activation in black women with TNBC.

22 This note describes activation of epidermal growth factor family genes ERBB2 and ERBB3 (HER2 and
23 HER3) in the tumors of black women with TNBC. Thus, together with evidence we present separately, we
24 describe discovery of fundamental haplotype-specific differences in expression of the hormone receptors
25 and of the growth factor (HER2) that define breast cancer in humans, but in hormone receptor negative
26 breast cancer (TNBC). Thus, while PGR and ESR1 were hormone receptor pathway components
27 of the tumor transcriptome determined by the haplotype in white women, HER2 was also identified as a
28 signature, race-determined hormone receptor pathway expression difference in humans with TNBC,
ERBB2 was activated with presence instead in black women.

Note 13: Molecules that function in Xist activation or that interact with Xist ncRNA are expressed
differently in TNBC resulting from the human genetic background.

The major target of Xist at autosomal targets and Xist interacting protein, interleukin enhancer factor ILF2,
KH-domain KHSRP, Menin, as well as multiple hnRNP transcripts. DNA repair molecules known to exert
activating or repressive control of Xist expression were also isolated here, including BRCA1 and MDC1,
expressed in the primary tumor in human TNBC in a haplotype (race)-dependent manner.

Note 14: Genes that function in DNA methylation are members of the TNBC gene signature whose
expression is significantly inflicted by genetic background.

This included TET3 and Dot1L, which were expressed at significantly higher quantity in the primary tumor
in black women with TNBC.

Note 15: Major differences in expression of multi-drug resistance ATP-binding cassettes in human TNBC
resulting from the genetic background (race).

1 A general pattern of MDR “pump” (channel) activation was observed in black women with TNBC. Genes
2 expressed at significant quantity in TNBC that were not influenced by genetic background were also
3 identified.

4 Note 16: Nucleotide synthesis expression differences are features of the TNBC transcriptome.

5 The human haplotype (race related genetic background in white and black humans) was a major influence
6 on genes that are necessary components of DNA replication for division of the tumor cell, including
7 DTYMK and RRM2, activated in the TNBC tumor transcriptome in black humans. We separately describe
8 TK1 activation in black women as evidence of enhanced tumor cell proliferation in black women with
9 TNBC, together demonstrating altered nucleotide synthesis mechanics resulting from the haplotype
10 (race-resulting genetic background). Contrarily and interestingly, RRM2B was not at all influenced by
11 genetic background, while expressed in appreciable quantity in the TNBC tumor in humans.

12 Note 17: Growth factors expressed in the primary tumor in triple negative breast cancer regulated by the
13 race haplotype in humans.

14 This was characterized by differences in expression of VGF, HDGF and PGF, expressed at higher levels in
15 black women. IGF1 and PDGF-C, however, were expressed in higher quantities in the tumors of white
16 women in human TNBC.

17 Note 18. Rb1 tumor expression is modestly influenced by patient race in black women with TNBC.

18 The tumors of black women with TNBC featured modest but quantitatively significant reduction in Rb1
19 tumor suppressor gene expression. p53 was not influenced by the race-associated genetic background in
20 human TNBC. E2F factor activation in black women with TNBC is described separately, as evidence of
21 enhanced tumor proliferation (increased speed of the cancer cell in primary tumors in vivo) in black
22 women with TNBC. CDK6 haplotype regulation and activation in black women is described elsewhere.

23 Note 19: Polarity and EMT are influenced by the genetic background in humans with TNBC.

24 We discovered race-dependent differences in expression of genes with functions in establishment and
25 changes in polarity including Vangl2, as well as genes that function to activate the EMT in cancer or to
26 execute EMT-associated functions, including SNAI2.

27 Note 20: Metabolism of the tumor is influenced by haplotype in humans with TNBC.

28 Genes with functions in cellular metabolism in redox biology, in fatty acid biosynthesis and other
processes were controlled by factors in the genetic background in humans with TNBC, including aldehyde
dehydrogenase ALDH16L1, CIAO2B, BCKDK, sirtuin family gene SIRT1, NOX4, and thioredoxin pathway
gene TXNDC12 were genes whose differential expression were signatures differences in tumor
transcriptome in TNBC resulting from differences in haplotype (the genetic background of white and black
humans).

Note 21: Transposon machinery and retroviral element expression is controlled by haplotype in human
TNBC.

This included the human transposases jumping translocation breakpoint JTB, piggybac transposase
PGBD and SETMAR.

ERVK13-1 was activated in white women with TNBC, but ERVMER34-1 was activated in black women.

Evidence of piwi pathway expression regulation by the human haplotype in human TNBC is also
presented. Genetic background in humans influences expression of transposase genetic mobilization

1 machinery, activation of endogenous retroviral elements and the expression of molecules that function in
2 RNAi-like gene regulation.

3 Note 22: Developmental or embryonic stem cell gene expression

4 This set of genes influenced by factors in the genetic background attributable to patient race in humans
5 with TNBC included RXRA and Wnt11, which was activated in the primary tumor in white women.

6 Note 23: Kinase expression of the lymphocyte expressed in breast cancers is enhanced in white women.

7 Enrichment of lymphocyte kinase expression in the primary tumors in white women with TNBC included
8 TEC and BTK kinases. The kinase SRC was modestly enriched in the tumors of black women.

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